

SLW were significant independent variables ($P < 0.03$) for predicting leaf N concentration in both greenhouse and field studies. With three SPAD readings per leaf blade in each case, the proportion of variability in leaf N concentration that the independent variable accounted for increased from 81 to 86% in the greenhouse study and

from 74 to 78% in the field study when based on SPAD values alone vs the combination of SPAD values and SLW as independent variables (see table).

Using a chlorophyll meter to monitor the N status of the rice plant may provide a useful tool for managing research experiments and varietal trials where adequate N supply must be maintained in

diverse environments and on different soils. Data, however, should be interpreted with caution because the SLW can influence the SPAD reading. If leaf N estimates need to be more accurate than SPAD readings, then the SLW should also be determined. This process is much simpler and faster than using the kjeldahl method to determine N. □

Fertilizer management—**inorganic sources**

Nutrient management for cotton - rice cropping system

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Cotton *Gossypium hirsutum* L. is grown in Srivilliputtur during Feb-Mar under summer irrigated conditions following wet-season rice. A short-duration pulse is generally grown during Aug-Sep between the cotton and rice crops in this system.

We studied nutrient management for cotton - green gram - rice during 1991 - 92. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with four replications. The soil at the site represents the tract and is a sandy clay loam with low available N, medium P, and high K. Short-duration cotton variety SVPR 1 was sown during Apr 1991, and the second crop, green gram KM2, was grown during Sep 1991. This was

Crop yields in a cotton-rice system in Srivilliputtur, Tamil Nadu, India, 1991-92. ^a

Treatment			Yield (t/ha)		
Cotton 60-30-30 kg NPK/ha	Pulse 25-50-0 kg NPK/ha	Rice 100-50-50 kg NPK/ha	Cotton	Green gram	Rice
Full NPK	Full NP	Full NPK	0.78	0.33	4.1
N	Full NP	Full NPK	0.74	0.33	4.0
N	P	Full NPK	0.74	0.32	4.0
N	No fertilizer	Full NPK	0.75	0.24	3.8
No fertilizer	No fertilizer	Full NPK	0.49	0.23	3.8
Full NPK	No fertilizer	Full NPK	0.77	0.26	3.9
No fertilizer	No fertilizer	Full NPK plus preen gram stubble	0.50	0.23	4.2
LSD (0.05)			0.06	0.03	ns

^a ns = not significant.

followed by IR20, which was transplanted in Nov 1991 with different fertilizer levels.

There was a clear response when NPK was applied to cotton and green gram under rice - fallow conditions. Cotton yields with 60-30-30 kg NPK/ha and 60 kg N/ha alone were similar. In the succeeding green gram, the yield was higher when 25 kg N and 22 kg P/ha were applied, which was on par with 22 kg P/ha

alone. In this sequence, the rice crop had a uniform application of the recommended dose of NPK fertilizers. Rice yield was not affected by fertilizer treatments in the preceding crops.

These results indicate the significance of the recommended 60 kg N/ha for summer cotton, 22 kg P/ha for a pulse crop, and NPK for a wet-season rice crop in the cropping system studied (see table). □

Fertilizer management—**organic sources**

Breaking seed dormancy in *Sesbania rostrata*

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Sesbania rostrata has potential as a leguminous green manure for lowland fields in many countries. But its thick,

hard seed covering can cause problems for growers.

We tested several methods to break seed dormancy using hot water, sulfuric acid, scrubbing with sand, and scrubbing and soaking in hot water.

Scrubbing seeds with sand for 5 min and/or soaking in hot water (about 60 °C) for 15 min were not very effective.

Treating seeds with concentrated H₂SO₄

Germination of *S. rostrata* seed under different treatments.

Treatment	Observation (no.)	Germination rate (%) ^a
Control	4	12.00 ± 3.61
Hot water for 15 min	4	17.25 ± 2.77
Scrubbing with sand for 5 min	3	12.33 ± 1.70
Scrubbing + hot water	3	20.00 ± 2.94
H ₂ SO ₄ concentrated	7	94.39 ± 4.06
Fast washing	3	6.13 ± 0.72
Slow washing	3	15.67 ± 1.88
H ₂ SO ₄ diluted	3	

^a Mean ± standard error.